

GreenFORCE

Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

D3.7_Report on the 1st Stand-alone Teaching Event

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List of project partners

Number	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country	PIC
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Executive Summary

D3.7 Report on the 1st Stand-alone Teaching Event details the activities conducted during the inaugural Summer School in Turin, Italy. In line with the project's General Agreement, GreenFORCE organized three intensive international summer schools, also referred to as stand-alone teaching events, to disseminate knowledge generated by the project itself.

Aligned with the project's main theme, "Just Green Transitions," the Turin Summer School focused on the post-carbon transformations of the city, chosen strategically as a key point for discussing the various implications of Just Green Transitions. The outcomes were shared with numerous stakeholders and representatives of the Turin municipality.

This deliverable outlines the activities carried out during the summer school and the contributions made by each partner. To facilitate understanding, the report is divided into six sections. Following this summary is a brief overview of the entire project (section 1). Section 2 elaborates on the significance of organizing summer schools as a means of sharing and co-generating knowledge, while section 3 provides insights into the importance of GreenFORCE's summer schools and their scheduling. Section 4 delves into the selected topic, offering a detailed overview of the organizational aspects of the summer school, including the methodology and main steps. Section 5 provides a comprehensive description of the activities conducted for each step, encompassing the kick-off, in-person meetings, and post-event online discussions. Section 6 presents briefly the final results of the summer school and offers an overview of products elaborated by each team.

For additional context, five annexes have been appended at the end of the report.

1. Project Overview

GreenFORCE aims at fostering excellence in the "Western Balkans' green transition" scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia) as a means to enhancing their research profile, strengthening research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans (WB) and EU research capacities, as well as to broader policy initiatives for the WB region. To achieve this objective, a twinning partnership of five organisations will work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; transferring and exchanging knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle, engaging in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level. Ultimately, the ambition is to transcend from individual learning to enabling institutional learning, ensuring that scientific research and its management practices become institutionalised within the recipient organisations. GreenFORCE will contribute to the impacts of the destination "Improved access to excellence" by enabling pathways of cooperation, exchange, co-design, and co-creation with academia, civil society and policymakers at the regional level. The five partner organisations are Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development in Albania as the coordinating partner; University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography (UB-GEF) in Serbia and the Center for Economic Analysis Association (CEA) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and Nordregio, a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden, together with Politecnico di Torino, Italy (POLITO), as the leading EU research institutions. POLIS University in Albania is the affiliate partner of Co-PLAN.

2. Why is important to organise Stand-alone Teaching Event

In general terms, organizing a stand-alone teaching event offers a range of benefits, including focused learning, targeted audience engagement, expert showcasing, networking opportunities, flexibility, resource optimization, effective marketing, measurable impact, time efficiency, and the promotion of innovation and creativity in education. More importantly, this format offers the opportunity to co-create knowledge based on a collaborative approach among students, tutors, and teachers with different experiences, backgrounds, and levels of understanding. Stand-alone teaching events are thus important for:

- *Offering multiple learning experiences:* allowing for a concentrated and focused learning experience on a specific topic or skill. Participants delve deep into the subject matter without the distraction of unrelated content.
- *Targeting specific audience:* these kind of events are usually tailored to a specific audience with common interests or needs.
- *Networking opportunities:* participants in stand-alone teaching events often share a common interest, making it easier for them to connect with like-minded individuals. This can enhance the overall learning experience and facilitate future collaboration.
- *Innovation and Creativity:* a stand-alone teaching event provides a platform for innovation and creativity in education. It allows for experimentation with different teaching methodologies, formats, and interactive elements to enhance the learning experience.

3. Stand-alone Teaching Events in GreenFORCE

According to the Grant Agreement (page 24), all partners are engaged in organizing and implementing three stand-alone teaching events that contribute to the co-design/co-evaluation, exchange, and sharing of the research practice and results conducted in WP4. The events should be open to master's and Ph.D. students from U_POLIS, UB-GEF, and POLITO. Each event will host up to 20 students, of which 50% will be from the hosting institution. The guest institutions will bring five students and two researchers each. According to the project timetable, the stand-alone teaching events are organized as follows:

- September 2023, Turin, Italy
- May, 2024, Belgrade, Serbia
- April/May, 2025, Tirane, Albania

As agreed, the teaching staff is composed of researchers from the five partner institutions (see annex 4). Operationally, students are selected in advance through an open call, and the events enable researchers to produce and exchange knowledge on the just green transition. To communicate this activity, the project web site has a dedicated section - [Summer School – GreenFORCE \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](https://greenforcetwinning.net).

4. Summer School Organisation

The summer school in Turin was organised jointly by the [Interuniversity Department of Urban and Regional Studies and Planning](#) and the [Interdepartmental Responsible Risk Resilience Centre \(R3C\)](#) of Politecnico di Torino and is set in the framework of the School of Planning and Design and supported by [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) in Albania as the coordinating partner; [University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography \(UB-GEF\)](#) in Serbia and the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden. It aimed to involve students from different universities in identifying the challenges and opportunities of just and green transitions in Turin's post-carbon city context. The main challenge was operationalising the green transition principles in the study's specific context. To face it, spatial and landscape planning instruments and decision-making strategies should be coordinated within a coherent and integrated framework. The students attended several lectures and working group activities that introduced the challenges they will have to focus on and present possible ways to approach them. Besides the local perspective, students learned from European and Western Balkans examples and case studies, being supervised and mentored by an international, multi-disciplinary teaching staff during their activity.

The summer school was organized in the following dates: 5 July 2023 (online kick-off meeting), 18-22 September 2023 (activities in Turin), 23 October 2023 (online intermediate presentations) and 23 November 2023 (final presentations). The involved universities and institutions were: Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development (coordinating partner, AL); Polis University (AL); Politecnico di Torino – R3C Responsible Risk Resilience Centre (IT), Nordregio (SE), University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography (RS) and Center for Economic Analyses Association (MK). The summer school involved 20 students from Politecnico di Torino, University of Belgrade and Polis University.

4.1 The Topic: “Cities in Just Green Transitions. Towards a 2030 climate-neutral strategy for Turin”

Turin is acknowledged as the most representative “Italian industrial city”, where FIAT and other important brands have developed starting from the end of the 1800. In the 60th and 70th the city’s industrial system employed around 300.000 workers. With the industrial crisis that started in the 1980s and exacerbated in the 1990s, the city took initiative to renovate its image and reshape its development future, at the same time favouring the reconversion of its industrial sites stock, mostly located on the central backbone railway – the so-called “Spina Centrale”. Whereas the conversation of Turin’s industrial areas, has required intense planning efforts and the action of a complex urban governance regime, the transition is to certain extent still ongoing, as the city continue to face challenges related to depopulation, pollution, industrial specialization and socio-spatial marginalization, just to name a few. In this regard, the City of Turin has been recently selected by the European Commission as one of the 100 (<https://eurocities.eu/latest/the-100-climate-neutral-and-smart-cities-by-2030/>) to become an essential hub of experimentation and innovation about climate matters at a European level. According to the program, the selected cities are meant to lead Europe’s zero-carbon transition, in turn contributing to

enhancing well-being through adequate decarbonisation efforts. The European Commission's Mission Board supports and guides them in this challenge for climate-neutral and smart cities through a multi-level, co-creative process that will be formalised in a Climate City Contract tailored to each city. The Mission Board is fully anchored in Europe's Green Deal strategy to make Europe climate-neutral by 2050. The achievement of zero carbon in an inclusive manner needs systemic reasoning and strategies to be pursued by cities. Accordingly, at the local level, the City of Turin is already beginning a dialogue with key institutions and strategic partners in the area to jointly pursue actions that can enable the ambitious goal of climate neutrality.

This Summer School positioned within this articulated process, and challenged the selected students to explore possible transition and transformation paths, in so doing, learning from the experience of Turin lessons that could then be transferred and adapted in other contexts in Europe and beyond. More in general, students will be invited to reflect on the just and green transitions as complex, multi-faceted phenomena that redefine mainstream development models towards a more socio-environmental and carbon-neutral society.

4.2 Summer School Main Organization Steps

The organization of the summer school in Turin followed three main steps (see Figure 1): (i) Step 1 - co-design of the summer school topic with partners and preparation of the call lead by POLITO; Step 2 - launching of the call and students' selection (while POLITO coordinated the process while each partner followed internal rules depending on the each institutional organization); Step 3 - the summer school implementation. Each step required specific actions/activities to implement and coordinate.

Figure 1 - 1st Stand-alone Teaching Event in Turin: timetable and main steps

Summer School Topic Definition

As the task lead and host institution, POLITO took the initiative to compile a comprehensive list of potential topics aligned with the principles of just green transitions. This list was then shared with the project partners for collective consideration. To ensure the relevance and depth of these topics, the project team engaged in ad hoc meetings where each partner contributed to refining and providing additional details to the proposed subjects. The criteria guiding this collaborative refinement process were:

- *Consistency and Coherence with Just Green Transitions*: Ensuring that the selected topics align seamlessly with the overarching principles and objectives of just green transitions, fostering a cohesive and unified approach to the project's goals.
- *Relevance (Nationally and Internationally)*: Evaluating the significance of each topic on both national and international scales, taking into account the specific interests expressed by each partner. This approach helps in tailoring the content to meet the diverse needs and priorities of the participating institutions.
- *Capacity and Knowledge Sharing*: Assessing the collective capacity and knowledge held by the partners on each topic. This criterion ensures that the chosen subjects leverage the expertise and insights available within the consortium, fostering a collaborative environment for meaningful knowledge exchange.
- *Relevance for the Territory (Turin Municipality and Main Stakeholders)*: Considering the impact and applicability of the selected topics within the local context, particularly focusing on the interests of Turin Municipality and other key stakeholders. This criterion helps in aligning the project outcomes with the specific needs and challenges of the project's immediate surroundings.

Through a collaborative and iterative process, these criteria have guided the selection and detailing of topics, ensuring that the stand-alone teaching events are academically robust and closely tailored to the unique context and goals of the project.

Call Preparation

POLITO has coordinated the preparation of the call in conjunction with all partners involved. As Annex 1 shows, a document was prepared including some info regarding among the others:

- The focus and main activities;
- The context -Turin post-carbon city which include a brief exploration of the case study;
- Eligibility Requirements, language, ECTS credits;
- Selection Criteria and Ethics.

The Launch of the summer school

The call has been launched simultaneously by each partner and communicated by the project website at the following link - [International Summer School with the theme 'Cities in Just Green Transitions'](#) and

a focus on 'Turin post-carbon transformations' in Turin, Italy on 18-22 September, 2023 – GreenFORCE (greenforcetwinning.net)

Student Selection

Students have been selected by each institution according to the following criteria (see annex 2 – list of students):

The students have been selected on the basis of the following criteria:

- interest-driving learning in the contents of the summer school students are applying to (i.e., operationalising just and green transition) based on the motivation letter;
- background and preparation based on the CV and/or the portfolio;
- research skills and attitudes based on the CV and/or the portfolio;

An evaluation committee composed of institutional staff involved in the teaching activity assessed the candidates. The list of selected candidates ensured a balanced representation of gender. No discrimination has been based on nationality, sexual orientation, or political opinion. Each institution guaranteed to maintain a selection process that is fair and equitable, and support informed and responsible decision-making of candidates.

The summer school activity is explained in the following section.

5. Summer school main activity conducted

5.1 Online Kick-off

The online kick-off meeting of the international Summer School "Cities in Just Green Transitions. Towards a 2030 climate-neutral strategy for Turin" was held on the 5th of July 2023. The event involved the 20 international students from U_Polis (Albania), UB-GEF (Serbia) and Polito. The teaching staff also involved international researchers from the 5 partner institutions: CEA (North Macedonia), Co-PLAN (Albania), Nordregio (Sweden), UB-GEF and U_Polis. The general topic of Just Green Transition was introduced in the context of a post-industrial city like Torino, that is part of the 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030 in Horizon Europe. The online meeting was organized with an opening and welcoming, then a presentation of the GreenFORCE project was proposed to the students. An introduction to the summer school topic, methodology, agenda and main activities was shared and partners' and students' had the opportunity to present themselves. A first introduction to the topic of Just Green Transitions¹ has been delivered by Alberto Giacometti (Nordregio).

¹¹ The presentation is available online at the following link: greenforcetwinning.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/JGT-concept-GreenFORCE-Teaching-Torino-Nordregio-in-kick-off.pdf

After the kick-off, a Preparatory Report (See annex 5) has been prepared by POLITO and sent to students in order to get familiarity with Turin challenges and the concept of Just Green Transitions.

5.2 In-presence Summer School in Turin

POLITO hosted the in-presence activities of the Summer School from the 18th to the 22nd of September 2023. The general topic of Just Green Transition is tested in the context of a post-industrial city like Turin, that is part of the 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030 in Horizon Europe.

On the first day, after an opening and welcoming with Andrea Longhi, Vice Head of DIST, Grazia Brunetta, Coordinator of R3C, and Giancarlo Cotella, GreenFORCE POLITO Team Coordinator, a synthetic introduction of the summer school was provided by Erblin Berisha and Elena Todella. Then, a theoretical introduction was provided on “Territorial Resilience and Just Green Transitions²” by Grazia Brunetta and Ombretta Caldarice, from R3C. Since Green Transition could be framed within the resilience-oriented policies and plans, the lecture framed the concept of territorial resilience, from its roots in ecology to resilience thinking in spatial planning welcoming the just green transition in the planning process. Also, Elena Deambrogio from the Municipality of Torino, Smart City, European Planning and Innovation, Torino City Lab, allowed students to go in-depth into the case study with the presentation “Turin in the 100 Climate Neutral Cities Mission”. Then, the first exercise on “Spatialisation of Just Green Transition Impacts³”, was launched by Andrea Ajmar, Politecnico di Torino, and Aleksandar Djordjevic, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography. Since geomatics’ techniques, remote sensing, and GIS, play a consolidated and scientifically recognised role in urban and regional planning and for implementing just green transitions (JGT) policies and interventions, the exercise let students learn a set of indicators representative of JGT, how to analyse and spatialize them through GIS techniques.

² The presentation is available online at the following link: [Brunetta & Caldarice Summer School GreenForce 18.09.2023 sintesi \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](#)

³ The presentation is available online at the following link: [greenforcetwinning.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/AndreaAleks-Spatio-temporal-variability-of-Just-Green-Transitions-indicators-Theory.pdf](#)

The second day was meant to deepen the case study, with the whole day organized by Urban Lab, an urban agency and autonomous association created to narrate the transformation processes of Turin and the metropolitan area. Students were provided with a presentation by Quirino Spinelli, Municipality of Torino, Turin City Planning Department staff, on “Rethinking Turin: challenges, strategies, opportunities”, and an introduction on “The post-industrial transformation of Turin”, by Chiara Lucchini, Urban Lab Territorial Development. Also, in the afternoon they were accompanied by Urban Lab through a city visit on the most significant post-carbon areas in Turin. The tour touched relevant spaces like Dora Park, that covers an area of 45 hectares where the five industrial areas Ingest, Vitali, Mortara, Valdocco and Michelin once stood. Elaborated following an international competition based on Jean-Pierre Buffi and Andreas Kipar's masterplan, the project by Germany's Latz + Partner with Turin-based Studio Pession recycles materials, structures and routes from the old iron and steel works, metallurgical factories, and tyre factories. Also, Bee Ozanam is located in a former industrial complex with an original “ship-machine” architecture, as a regenerated space in the name of sustainability with vegetable gardens and roof gardens, a social restaurant, an apiary, and an open and inclusive community hub where ideas, projects and activities can be generated. Then, Baldissera Square has been visited, as one of the most talked about road junctions in the city due to frequent traffic jams and the cause of strong complaints from citizens. Nearby, the project to redevelop a long railway trench on Via Saint Bon, where the Turin-Ceres line originally ran, was presented as a way to recover the now disused tunnel between the Madonna di Campagna neighborhood and the Dora. Along the Dora River, where “metal” gasometers stand as evidence of the city's industrial past (former Italgas area), sits the new Einaudi Campus, home to the Law and Political Science faculties of the University of Turin. The project signed by Foster & Partners, Camerana & Partners, Tecnimont, Mellano Associati and Giugiaro Architettura, winners of an international competition, creates an organic system of seven pavilions with ribbon facades, arranged around a large circular plaza. Between Campus Einaudi and the adjacent student housing the visit continued with Ottavio Mario Mai street, the subject of a recent redevelopment by the City of Torino. With about 4,500 square meters of pedestrian area equipped for the benefit of students and citizens, this project is part of the interventions financed through the European project Urban Innovative Actions, aimed at improving the livability of public spaces in the areas adjacent to the Dora River, including in the

evening and night hours. The tour ended in Off Topic, a center for youth protagonism born thanks to a bet made by the Torino Youth Centre, an association that in 2017 decided to invest in the renovation of spaces for the creation of a new hub for the city.

On the third day, students were involved in a second exercise on socio-economic analyses, with multiple presentations, such as “Cost-Benefit Analysis: an approach to measure Just Green Transition⁴”, by Merita Toska, Co-PLAN – Institute for Habitat Development and “A case study in North Macedonia: cost-benefit analysis for coal thermal plant decommissioning⁵”, Vesna Garvanlieva, Center for Economic Analysis (CEA).

These lectures introduced the audience to the Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) and the Social Environmental Cost Benefit Analysis (SE-CBA) as an instrument to assess, among others, the impact of green transition actions. Also, students were introduced to an applied exercise. The aim was combining a short theoretical part followed by an example of practical perspective of what an input-output analysis is and how it may be used. The third exercise was related to “Land-Based Financing⁶”, by Kejt Dhrami, Co-PLAN – Institute for Habitat Development. The session introduced an emerging approach that seeks to harness the potential of land markets to fund and promote sustainable land use practices and nature-based solutions. The aim was to equip students with a background understanding of land markets, value capture instruments, and surplus value calculations (residual land value for public use) in the context of resilient urban development. The presentation was complemented by a gaming exercise, where a land purchase process was simulated with students, empowered to explore innovative ways to finance and implement climate solutions, contributing to a more resilient future.

⁴ The presentation is available online at the following link: greenforcetwinning.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Cost-Benefit-Analysis_Merita-Toska.pdf

⁵ The presentation is available online at the following link: [PowerPoint Presentation \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](#)

⁶ The presentation is available online at the following link: [PowerPoint Presentation \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](#)

On the fourth day, a further presentation and exercise was proposed on “Just Green Transition: between carbon-neutrality and (re)industrialisation⁷”, by Carlos Tapia and Alberto Giacometti, Nordregio. The students were pushed to challenge the dominant narrative of the JGT which focuses on the negative impacts (on labour) of decommissioning 'obsolete' industries and energy systems and brings to light the challenges of adaptation to new technological regimes and re-industrialisation. The teaching staff introduced the case study areas and detailed material related to planning challenges, socio-economic trends, and governance context, then students were involved in a practical exercise to work on planning and strategic solutions. Also, at the end of the afternoon, students were welcomed again by Andrea Bocco, Head of the Department, DIST, Politecnico di Torino.

On the last day, intermediate presentations of the groups' work were organized, with a discussion and a wrap-up. The five groups of students presented their work-in-progress strategies for Turin, with the possibility of reaching comments and suggestions through a roundtable with professors and tutors.

5.3 1st Online Meeting

The activities of the Summer School “Cities in Just Green Transitions. Towards a 2030 climate-neutral strategy for Turin” continued online. On the 23rd of October 2023 students discussed a draft of their strategies, producing and exchanging knowledge on just green transitions. The intermediate presentations of the groups' work was followed by a discussion and wrap-up, then by a roundtable with professors and tutors. Some final remarks and next steps was then proposed.

⁷ The presentation is available online at the following link : greenforcetwinning.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/2023_GreenFORCE-Summer-School_Nordregio-final_compressed.pdf

5.4 2nd Online meeting

The final activities of the Summer School were conducted online on the 23rd of November 2023. The final report were presented by the students and discussed with the professors, tutors and mentors. The collected materials were commented and delivered in order to be shared with the Municipality.

6. Summer school main results and outputs

The activity conducted allowed the students to work in a multidisciplinary and international environment. The 20 students have been organised in 5 teams, each constituted by 4 students (2 from POLITO, 1 from UB-GEF and 1 from U_Polis). Here we offer a brief contextualisation of the topics addressed by each team.

Team 1 focused on “Torino Digital Renaissance Initiative Fostering Digital Progress and Sustainable Urban Evolution in Torino”⁸.

The project focused on the rejuvenation of Torino's post-industrial sites, strategically located in the heart of the city and of considerable size, drawing significant attention from the municipal authorities. With an eye toward the digital future, this initiative unfolds across three pivotal dimensions:

- **Museum of the Future:** This facet functions as a vibrant showcase space, bringing together companies in the digital urban solutions sector. Here, they can exhibit prototype products, engaging the general public to gather real-time feedback for product refinement. Furthermore, this space generates revenue through registration fees and data access, fueling innovation in urban technology.
- **Digital Low-Skill Worker Hub:** Recognizing the evolving employment landscape, the project identifies the demand for low-skill digital workers. The hub offers training in tasks like data entry, document formatting, and social media management, catering to that group of people that is often marginalized or cannot integrate into the workforce.
- **Monitoring Office for Autonomous Cities:** In response to the ongoing global shift toward autonomous cities, this component addresses the absence of comprehensive monitoring. It develops essential indicators to assess the integration, effectiveness, durability, functionality, and societal implications of digital technologies in urban settings. This data-driven approach empowers informed decision-making, fosters sustainability, and advances urban research.

By repurposing these post-industrial sites, the project not only catalyzes digital transformation but also stimulates economic growth, education, and research, making Torino take the first steps toward a pioneering city in the digital age.

Team 2 devoted their attention to the issue of “ENERGY EQUI(Pover)TY Through addressing energy security”⁹

In this respect, energy poverty poses a significant and far-reaching challenge in numerous societies, profoundly impacting the well-being and quality of life for individuals. A fundamental measure used to

⁸ The final report of Team 1 is available at the following link: [Final-Report Team-1 Torino-Summer-School.pdf \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](#)

⁹ The final report of Team 2 is available at the following link: [Final-Report Team-2 Torino-Summer-School.pdf \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](#)

gauge energy poverty is the energy efficiency rating of residential buildings, a vital tool for assessing buildings' energy efficiency and pinpointing families and communities facing elevated energy expenses.

The analysis of energy poverty can be conducted at multiple levels, namely meso, macro, and micro. On a meso scale, geographic regions with the highest energy poverty rates can be identified. On a macro level, the effectiveness of national and regional energy policies in addressing this issue can be evaluated. At a micro level, a detailed examination of the specific conditions of households and housing is possible.

In response to these challenges, innovative solutions have been crafted. These solutions involve enhancing the potential for deducting project costs, potentially up to 100%, based on the scope of the intervention and the poverty level. If this strengthened incentive falls short, measures to incentivize private or institutional entities may be implemented. The United Kingdom's 'Energy Company Obligation' serves as a notable example, providing subsidies to energy providers obliged to implement energy-efficient measures in residential buildings occupied by vulnerable individuals. Annual targets are set to reduce energy consumption and lower energy bills, with intervention costs shared among electric and gas service users. Additionally, proposals to enable the transfer of tax credits to consortia of financial institutions, offering low-interest rates to individuals experiencing energy poverty, aim to alleviate the burden on those most affected.

Team 3 decided to focus on GREEN INFRASTRUCTURE AND CLIMATE CHANGE. Subtitle Green Infrastructure and Sustainable Mobility¹⁰

More precisely, Turin's "city transition" represents a profound shift towards sustainability, climate resilience, and environmental stewardship, addressing climate change and environmental challenges. This transformation envisions urban areas as hubs of sustainability and social equity, committing to replace resource-intensive and environmentally harmful practices with sustainable, low-carbon, and socially inclusive alternatives.

Central to this change are green infrastructure and sustainable mobility, led by the pioneering "Multipurpose Transportation System project in microzones." This project not only enhances sustainable mobility but introduces a variety of vehicles, including electric buses, bicycles, electric scooters, and pedestrian-friendly pathways. These diverse vehicles within the project promote a multi-modal and eco-friendly approach to mobility in Turin's microzones.

The green infrastructure initiative goes beyond the ordinary, establishing a "green corridors network" connecting natural urban elements such as green spaces, vertical gardens, water retention systems, and urban wetlands. This network contributes significantly to carbon sequestration, improved air quality, temperature regulation, flood mitigation, and biodiversity support.

¹⁰ The final report of Team 3 is available at the following link: greenforcetwinning.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Final-Report_Team-3_Torino-Summer-School.pdf

Turin's city transition identifies challenges and opportunities, charting a clear path towards sustainability and resilience. This comprehensive approach, now integrating a variety of vehicles, encapsulates Turin's vision for a greener, more sustainable, and environmentally responsible urban future.

Team 4 focused on SOCIAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE URBAN HEAT ISLAND EFFECT. Just and Green Transitions¹¹

This topic undertakes an in-depth examination of the social implications arising from Turin's Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect, with a specific focus on its impact on marginalized communities, addressing challenges posed by rising temperatures and prioritizing community well-being. The main strategy involves boosting Turin's green infrastructure, creating connected spaces, ecological corridors, and community centers to mitigate the UHI effect on marginalized communities and promote social equality. The cost-benefit analysis evaluates economic, social, and environmental impacts, emphasizing potential benefits like reduced heat stress, improved air quality, water management, community well-being, increased property values, and business attraction. The literature review explores Just Green Transitions, focusing on environmental justice and community participation. The methodology combines literature review, policy analysis, and data collection to understand UHI's social implications. Maps and data analysis reveal correlations between UHI risk, greenery, income, and foreigner concentration. Focusing on the neighborhoods of Aurora and Barriera di Milano, the case study proposes a strategy to enhance green infrastructure, reduce heat stress, and improve the well-being of the 90,197 inhabitants. Furthermore, the study challenges Turin's post-industrial narrative, emphasizing the need for green transitions in industrial areas. The policy recommendations advocate for inclusive green infrastructure development, considering economic impacts, and preventing gentrification through measures like rent control and just-cause evictions.

Team 5 attentioned the issue of "URBAN GREEN REGENERATION. Urban regeneration and sustainable mobility"¹²

More in detail, the aim of this study is to contribute to the development of Turin's Just Green Transition in the framework of public consultation and involvement in the process. It represents the vision of the students from Albanian (Polis University- Faculty of Urban Planning and Management), Serbian (University of Belgrade-Faculty of Geography) and Italian (Politecnico di Torino) Institutions, developed in the framework of Green Force project. Its findings are results of the lectures and workshops at the summer school extended by policy and strategy review, GIS data analysis, swot and pestle analysis, impact and cost benefit analysis, and synthesis. The whole project is built on suggesting a physical and social transition on the spatial dimension by supporting urban regeneration which is blended with green strategies to make Torino more climate-resilient and sustainable city. The synthesis resulted in policy recommendation targeting green urban regeneration with three following pillars greenery network,

¹¹ The final report of Team 4 is available at the following link: [Final-Report Team-4 Torino-Summer-School.pdf \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](#)

¹² The final report of Team 4 is available at the following link: [Final-Report Team-5 Torino-Summer-School compressed.pdf \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](#)

urban renovation, and social sustainability, and sustainable mobility along with one horizontal line: inclusion and just transition for the vulnerable classes with the suggested policy changes.

The final presentations prepared by the students can be accessed here - [PowerPoint Presentation \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](https://greenforcetwinning.net)

Annex 1 – Summer School Call

International Summer School

Cities in Just Green Transitions

Turin post-carbon transformations

Deadline for application
26.05.2023

Funded by the
European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

International Summer School

Cities in Just Green Transitions

Turin post-carbon transformations

Deadline for application

26.05.2023

Dates of the Summer School: 18-22 September 2023.

Eligible candidates: students enrolled in the Master of Sciences in “Pianificazione Territoriale, Urbanistica e Paesaggistico-Ambientale”, curriculum “Pianificare la città e il territorio”, “Territorial, Urban, Environmental and Landscape Planning”, curriculum “Planning for the Global Urban Agenda”, and “Digital Skills for Sustainable Societal Transitions”.

POLITO GreenFORCE Team: Giancarlo Cotella, Andrea Ajmar, Erblin Berisha, Grazie Brunetta, Ombretta Caldarice, Donato Casavola, Danial Mohabat Doost, Isabella M. Lami, Yahya Shaker, Elena Todella.

Involved universities and institutions: Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development (coordinating partner, AL); Polis University (AL); Politecnico di Torino – R3C Responsible Risk Resilience Centre (IT), Nordregio (SE), University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography (RS) and Center for Economic Analyses Association (MK).

The summer school involves up to 10 selected Polito students within the framework of the HORIZON-WIDERA project “GreenFORCE. Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans”.

The activity provides 2 ECTS credits to the participating students.

Project website: <https://greenforcetwinning.net/>

Contacts: erblin.berisha@polito.it; elena.todella@polito.it

Nordregio

University of Belgrade
FACULTY OF
GEOGRAPHY

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Focus and activities

The summer school in Turin is organised jointly by the [Interuniversity Department of Urban and Regional Studies and Planning](#) and the [Interdepartmental Responsible Risk Resilience Centre \(R3C\)](#) of Politecnico di Torino and is set in the framework of the School of Planning and Design and supported by [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) in Albania as the coordinating partner; [University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography \(UB-GEF\)](#) in Serbia and the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden.

It aims to involve students from different universities in identifying the challenges and opportunities of just and green transitions in Turin's post-carbon city context. The main challenge is operationalising the green transition principles in the study's specific context. To face it, spatial and landscape planning instruments and decision-making strategies should be coordinated within a coherent and integrated framework.

The students will attend several lectures and working group activities that introduce the challenges they will have to focus on and present possible ways to approach them. Besides the local perspective, students will learn from European and Western Balkans examples and case studies.

They will be supervised and mentored by an international, multi-disciplinary teaching staff during their activity.

Context – Turin post-carbon city

Turin is acknowledged as the most representative "Italian industrial city", where FIAT and other important brands have developed starting from the end of the 1800. In the 60th and 70th the city's industrial system employed around 300.000 workers. With the industrial crisis that started in the 1980s and exacerbated in the 1990s, the city took initiative to renovate its image and reshape its development future, at the same time favouring the reconversion of its industrial sites stock, mostly located on the central backbone railway – the so-called "spina centrale".

Whereas the conversation of Turin's industrial areas, has required intense planning efforts and the action of a complex urban governance regime, the transition is to certain extent still ongoing, as the city continue to face challenges related to depopulation, pollution, industrial specialization and socio-spatial marginalization, just to name a few. In this regard, the City of Turin has been recently selected by the European Commission as one of the 100 "[Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030](#)" to become an essential hub of experimentation and innovation about climate matters at a European level. According to the program, the selected cities are meant to lead Europe's zero-carbon transition, in turn contributing to enhancing well-being through adequate decarbonisation efforts. The European Commission's Mission Board supports and guides them in this challenge for climate-neutral and smart cities through a multi-level, co-creative process that will be formalised in a Climate City Contract tailored to each city. The Mission Board is fully anchored in Europe's Green Deal strategy to make Europe climate-neutral by 2050. The achievement of zero carbon in an inclusive manner needs systemic reasoning and strategies to be pursued by cities. Accordingly, at the local level, the City of Turin is already beginning a dialogue with key institutions and strategic partners in the area to jointly pursue actions that can enable the ambitious goal of climate neutrality.

This summer school positions within this articulated process, and it challenges the selected students to explore possible transition and transformation paths, in so doing, learning from the experience of Turin lessons that could then be transferred and adapted in other contexts in Europe and beyond. More in general, students will be invited to reflect on the just and green transitions as complex, multi-faceted phenomena that redefine mainstream development models towards a more socio-environmental and carbon-neutral society.

Language

The activity will be exclusively held in English. Please specify your level of English in the application document.

Eligibility Requirements

Eligible students are enrolled in the Master of Sciences in “Pianificazione Territoriale, Urbanistica e Paesaggistico-Ambientale”, curriculum “Pianificare la città e il territorio”, “Territorial, Urban, Environmental and Landscape Planning”, curriculum “Planning for the Global Urban Agenda”, and “Digital Skills for Sustainable Societal Transitions”.

ECTS Credits

The participating students will be awarded 2 ECTS credits.

Fees and Obligations

The programme does not require the payment of any fee. The costs covered by the organisation include:

- 5-day intensive summer school in Torino (Castello del Valentino) with lectures and studio work;
- 1 social dinner;
- 5 lunches and coffee breaks;
- site visit to selected case study area;
- multidisciplinary tutoring from teaching staff from PoliTO, Co-PLAN, U_Polis, Nordregio, UB-GEF and CEA during the academic activities of the summer school.

Participants are required to bring their laptops.

How to participate

Each candidate should fill out the dedicated [Google form](#) and provide, by uploading to the system, the following additional information:

- a motivational letter (max 800 words) written in English;
- a Curriculum Vitae (CV) and/or a portfolio, including the POLITO’s M.Sc. list of exams successfully passed and the achieved marks.

Selection Criteria and Ethics

Candidates will be assessed based on the information provided in the motivation letter and in the CV, or portfolio.

The 10 PoliTO students will be selected on the basis of the following criteria:

- interest-driving learning in the contents of the summer school students are applying to (i.e., operationalising just and green transition) based on the motivation letter;
- background and preparation based on the CV and/or the portfolio;
- research skills and attitudes based on the CV and/or the portfolio;

An evaluation committee composed of the PoliTO staff involved in the teaching activity will assess the candidates.

Ethics disclaimer: The list of selected candidates will ensure a balanced representation of gender. No discrimination will be based on nationality, sexual orientation, or political opinion. PoliTO will guarantee to maintain a selection process that is fair and equitable, and support informed and responsible decision-making of candidates.

List of Participants

An email will be sent to selected candidates on June the 1st, 2023. The list will comprise up to 10 selected students + 2 eligible candidates (reserve list).

The ten selected students shall email to erblin.berisha@polito.it and elena.todella@polito.it to communicate the acceptance of their position by June 7th, 2023. If one of the ten selected students cancels their participation in time, the first eligible candidate in the reserve list will take their place.

Disclaimer

The organization is NOT accountable if the activity is cancelled for any *force majeure* reason.

General timeline

Dates	Before the summer school
15th of May 2023	Launch of the Call for Participation
26th of May 2023	Deadline for students' application
1st of June 2023	Notification of the results
7th of June 2023	Deadline for acceptance and finalization of the list of participants
	Summer school and after
July 2023 (to be defined)	1-day meeting event (online)
18th-22nd of September 2023	summer school activities in Torino
October 2023 (to be defined)	2-days feedback event (online)

Summer School Teaching Staff

PoliTO – Giancarlo Cotella, Andrea Ajmar, Erblin Berisha, Grazie Brunetta, Ombretta Caldarice, Donato Casavola, Danial Mohabat Doost, Isabella M. Lami, Yahya Shaker, Elena Todella

Co-Plan – Merita Toska, Kejt Dhrami

Nordregio – Carlos Tapia, Alberto Giacometti

UB-GEF – Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic

CEA – Marjan Nikolov, Vesna Garvanlieva

GreenFORCE Project

This students' summer school is part of the HORIZON-WIDERA project "[GreenFORCE. Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans](#)" (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02-02). The five partner organisations are [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) in Albania as the coordinating partner; [University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography \(UB-GEF\)](#) in Serbia and the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden, together with [Politecnico di Torino \(PoliTO\)](#), in Italy, as the leading EU research institutions. POLIS University (U_Polis) in Albania is the affiliate partner of Co-PLAN.

GreenFORCE aims to foster excellence in the Western Balkans' green transition scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia); to enhance their research profile, strengthening the research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans and European Union research capacities, as well as to broader policy initiatives for the region. This objective is reached through the twinning partnership of five organisations that work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; transfer and exchange knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle; and engage in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level.

The researchers of the consortium engage in building a joint research project with objectives related to (i) the conceptualisation of green transition in the WB; (ii) the assessment of impacts and costs of just green transition, focusing on components of the pillars of the EU green agenda for the WB; (iii) the proposal of a continuous monitoring and assessment framework on green transition impacts and costs in the WB, to be used by scientists, researchers and policy-makers in facilitating the just green transition.

This summer school is the first of three stand-alone teaching events that contribute to the co-design, co-evaluation, exchange and sharing of the research practice and results conducted in the project. The events are open to students from U_Polis, UB-GEF and PoliTO. Each event will host up to 20 students, of which ten will be from the hosting institution, in this case, PoliTO. Students attending at least one of the stand-alone teaching events may decide to work more thoroughly on this topic through the development of their master thesis under the supervision of one or more professors involved in the summer school.

For any clarification, please send an email to both erblin.berisha@polito.it and elena.todella@polito.it.

The activity is organized with the support of the PoliTO School of Planning and Design.

Annex 2 – List of Students Selected

Students attending the summer school have agreed on sharing the material

Institution	Surname	Name
PoliTO	AMINRAD	Ramtin
PoliTO	AY	Cemre Betul
PoliTO	FARAHNAK	Narges
PoliTO	HERBAS LOUREIRO	Sofia
PoliTO	LIN	Yanya
PoliTO	NAZARI	Amirmehdi
PoliTO	SAFAEIANPOUR	Ali
PoliTO	SHIVA SHANKAR	Suhas
PoliTO	TARANTINO	Giulia
UPolis	DAJKO	Megi
UPolis	GORA	Alba
UPolis	HAXHIA	Leonora
UPolis	KALO	Irisa
UPolis	MUKA	Rea
UB-GEF	MILOŠEVIĆ	Branko
UB-GEF	PLANIĆ	Andrija
UB-GEF	POPOVIĆ	Vladimir
UB-GEF	SIMEUNOVIĆ	Jelena
UB-GEF	TOMOVIĆ	Lazar
UB-GEF	NIKOLOV	Ana

Annex 3 - The Summer School Agenda

The summer school was organised in three phases. The first phase is the summer school opening, organised online aiming at kick-off the activity. The second consisted of 5 days working activity held in Turin at the Politecnico di Torino, while the third phase foresaw 2 post-summer school meetings held online.

Day Zero – Kick-off Meeting, Wednesday 5th July 2023, 9:30 – 13.00 (CEST)

Online

- 9.30 – 10.00: Opening of the summer school and welcoming, **Giancarlo Cotella**, Politecnico di Torino
- 10.00 – 10.30: Presentation of the GreenFORCE project, **Anila Bejko (Gjika)**, Co-PLAN
- 10.30 – 11.00: Introduction to the summer school topic, methodology, agenda and main activities, **Erblin Berisha**, Politecnico di Torino
- 11.00 – 11.30: Partners' Presentations, **GreenFORCE members**
- 11.30 – 11.45: *Break*
- 11.45 – 12.15: Students' Presentations, **Students**
- 12.15 – 12.45: Setting the context: "Just" Green Transition, **Alberto Giacometti**, Nordregio
- 12.45 – 13.00: Final remarks and next steps, **Giancarlo Cotella**, Politecnico di Torino

Day 1 – Monday 18th September 2023, 9:00 - 18.00 (CEST)

Venue: Valentino Castle, Address: Viale Mattioli, 39, 10125, Turin (Room: 4V)

- 9.00 – 9.30: Opening of the summer school and welcoming, **Andrea Longhi**, Vice Head of DIST, Politecnico di Torino, **Grazia Brunetta**, Coordinator of R3C, **Giancarlo Cotella**, **GreenFORCE POLITO Team Coordinator**, Politecnico di Torino
- 9.30 – 9.45: Introduction to the summer school (a synthesis), **Erblin Berisha and Elena Todella**, Politecnico di Torino
- 9.45 – 10.30: Territorial Resilience and Just Green Transitions, **Grazia Brunetta and Ombretta Caldarice**, R3C, Politecnico di Torino
- 10.30 – 11.00: *Coffee Break*
- 11.00 – 11.45: Turin in the 100 Climate Neutral Cities Mission, **Elena Deambrogio**, Municipality of Torino, Smart City, European Planning and Innovation, Torino City Lab
- 11.45 – 12.30: Summer school activities and outputs, **Erblin Berisha and Elena Todella**, Politecnico di Torino
- 12.30 – 13.00: Subdivision into groups, meeting with the tutors and organisation of the work
- 13:00 – 14:30: *Lunch break at [Caffetteria Universitaria](#)*
- 14.30 – 15.15: Spatialisation of Just Green Transition Impacts, **Andrea Ajmar**, Politecnico di Torino, and **Aleksandar Djordjevic**, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography
- 15:15 – 18.00: Work in the classroom under tutors' supervision
- From 19.00: Welcome reception and aperitif at [Casa del Quartiere](#), San Salvario, Turin

Day 2 – Tuesday 19th of September 2023, 09:30 - 17.30 (CEST)

Venue: Urban Lab, Address: [Piazza Palazzo di Città, 8ff, 10122, Turin](#)

- 9:45 – 10:30: Rethinking Turin: challenges, strategies, opportunities, **Quirino Spinelli**, Municipality of Torino, Turin City Planning Department staff
- 10.30 – 11.30: Welcome to Urban Lab. The post-industrial transformation of Turin, **Chiara Lucchini**, Urban Lab Territorial Development
- 11.15 – 11.45: *Coffee Break*
- 11.45 – 12.30: Introduction to the permanent Urban Lab exhibition and free visit by students
- 12:45 – 14:00 *Lunch box at Urban Lab*
- 14.00 – 17.30: City Visit, provided by Urban Lab

Day 3 – Wednesday 20th September 2023, 9:00 - 18.00 (CEST)

Venue: Valentino Castle, Address: [Viale Mattioli, 39, 10125, Turin \(Room: 4V\)](#)

- 9.00 – 09.45: Cost-Benefit Analysis: an approach to measure Just Green Transition, **Merita Toska**, Co-PLAN – Institute for Habitat Development
- 9.45 – 10.30: A case study in North Macedonia: cost-benefit analysis for coal thermal plant decommissioning, **Vesna Garvanlieva**, Center for Economic Analysis (CEA)
- 10.30 – 11.15: Land-Based Financing, **Kejt Dhrami**, Co-PLAN – Institute for Habitat Development
- 11.15 – 11.45: *Coffee Break*
- 11.45 – 13.00: Work in the classroom under tutors' supervision
- 13:00 – 14:30: *Lunch break at [Caffetteria Universitaria](#), San Salvario, Turin*
- 14.30 – 18.00: Work in the classroom under tutors' supervision
- From 20.00: Social Dinner, [Sciarada](#), San Salvario, Turin

Day 4 – Thursday 21st September 2023, 9:00 – 18.00 (CEST)

Venue: Valentino Castle, Address: [Viale Mattioli, 39, 10125, Turin \(Room: 4V\)](#)

- 9.00 - 10.00: Just Green Transition: between carbon-neutrality and (re)industrialisation, **Carlos Tapia and Alberto Giacometti**, Nordregio
- 10.00 – 13.00: Work in the classroom under tutors' supervision
- 13:00 – 14:30: *Lunch break at [Caffetteria Universitaria](#)*
- 14.30 – 18.00: Work in the classroom under tutors' supervision

Day 5 – 22nd September July 2023, 9:00 – 13.00 (CEST)

Venue: Valentino Castle, Address: [Viale Mattioli, 39, 10125, Turin \(Room: 4V\)](#)

- 9.00 – 9.10: Greetings from **Andrea Bocco**, Head of the Department, DIST, Politecnico di Torino
- 9.10 – 11.00: Intermediate presentations of the groups' work, discussion and wrap-up
- 11.00 – 12:30: Roundtable with professors and tutors
- 12.30 – 13.00: Final remarks and next steps, **Giancarlo Cotella**, Politecnico di Torino
- 13:00 – 14:30 *Lunch break at [Caffetteria Universitaria](#)*

Day 6 – Intermediate presentations, 23 October 2023, 9:30 - 12.30 (CEST)*Online*

- 9.30 – 11.30: Intermediate presentations of the groups' work, discussion and wrap-up
11.30 – 12.15: Roundtable with professors and tutors
12.15 – 12.30: Final remarks and next steps, **Giancarlo Cotella**, Politecnico di Torino

Day 7 – Final presentations, 23 November 2023, 9:30 - 12.30 (CEST)*Online*

- 9.30 – 12.15: Final presentations of the groups' work and comments from professors and tutors
12.15 – 12.30: Final remarks, **Giancarlo Cotella and Erblin Berisha**, Politecnico di Torino

Annex 4 – Teaching Staff

This summer school benefited from the contribution of more than 20 teachers/tutors. More specifically, as a hosting institute, POLITO involved 13 professors, teaching assistants and tutors, while the project partners contributed with a staff of 2 professors/experts per each. The following section provides the list of people involved in with a brief bio each.

Giancarlo Cotella (POLITO UNITE responsible) is associate professor at Politecnico di Torino. His research mainly focuses on European Territorial Governance, in particular on the mutual influence occurring between European Spatial Planning and the spatial governance and planning systems characterising the different Member States. He took active part to several international research projects as ESPON ReSSI, ESPON URRUC, ESPON COMPASS, ESPON SUPER, ESPON METRO, ERASMUS KA2 SPOT and LOTUS and the recently awarded Horizon Europe GreenFORCE and ESPON projects NoStaGeo and TERRES. Since 2023, he serves as Secretary General of the Association of European Schools of Planning.

Andrea Ajmar is an associate professor at Politecnico di Torino: he holds a doctorate in Environmental Geoengineering and is an expert in analysis in GIS environment and in the development and implementation of Spatial Data Infrastructures. He is a member of the SDG11Lab laboratory which aims to create a spatial data infrastructure capable of guaranteeing efficient access to data sources of general interest (e.g., satellite and airborne acquisitions, reference cartographic data, etc.) and integrate them with specific thematic data, providing analysis, representation, and visualization tools for research activities. He is involved in several research projects and in operational cartographic production services, both at the national and European level.

Erblin Berisha is assistant professor at Politecnico di Torino. His research focuses on the evolution of Spatial Planning Systems and Territorial Governance in the Western Balkan region in the light of international influence. He is also interested in understanding the geopolitical implications of international initiatives in the region. As research has been involved in numerous international projects like ESPON COMPASS, ESPON SUPER, ESPON SUPER spin-off, ESPON METRO, and more recently is taking an active part in the Horizon Europe GreenFORCE project and in the ESPON projects NoStaGeo and TERRES.

Grazia Brunetta is Professor of Urban Planning at DIST Politecnico di Torino. She is Scientific coordinator of the Responsible Risk Resilience interdepartmental Centre (R3C) of Politecnico di Torino, where she is the scientific coordinator of an interdisciplinary research team that aims to enhance cities forward resilience in planning and policy. Her main research activities show a deep and constant involvement in the field of urban and regional planning, with a particular focus on the innovation in the theories, methodologies, and approaches for spatial planning, in both research and academic teaching activity. She is the scientific coordinator of 2nd level specialising master programme in Metodi e Tecniche per il governo di territori resilienti. Verso la gestione integrata dei rischi. She is member of the Expert committee of the Intensive Training on Urban Resilience organized by University of Southern Denmark, Aalborg University, and BloxHub Copenhagen. She is the scientific coordinator of a wide range of research on regional and environmental planning, dealing with institutional innovation in spatial planning, evaluation in planning, spatial analysis for regional development, urban resilience in planning

and design. On these topics she has been coordinator of many international and national research teams and invited speaker in national and international conferences. She has authored more than 250 publications.

Ombretta Caldarice is Assistant Professor in Urban and Regional Planning at the Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST), Politecnico di Torino. She is a Faculty Affiliate Member of the Responsible Risk Resilience Centre - R3C, Politecnico di Torino. Her research activities focus on the interplay between planning and urban resilience through the lens of planning rules. She has more than ten years of international experience in research, capacity-building, and education on how to make cities more resilient, dealing with the following topics: (i) theories and practices of resilience; (ii) mainstreaming resilience in spatial planning; and (iii) urban codes and techniques for resilience. She is the co-coordinator of the ERASMUS+ Project with the Witwatersrand University Johannesburg on resilience and climate change. She is a member of the scientific committee of the Intensive Training on Urban Resilience (University of Southern of Denmark). She is a member of the Editorial Board of the Springer Book Series "Resilient Cities. Rethinking Urban Transformation."

Martina Caputo is a PhD student in Urban and Regional Development (DIST). She obtained her Master Degree in Urban and Territorial Planning - the international pathway Planning for the Global Urban Agenda. Currently she is a researcher at the Responsible Risk Resilience Centre - R3C, an interdisciplinary research centre of the Politecnico di Torino dedicated to territorial resilience. The main topics of her research are territorial resilience, adaptation and green transition, with a focus on EU policies. She also contributes to the course "Progettare la transizione resiliente di città e territori" of the project "Intraprendenti" (A.A. 2023/24 First Level Degree Course).

Donato Casavola is a PhD candidate in Urban and Regional Development at the Politecnico di Torino. His research activity is mainly related to issues of spatial planning and territorial governance in the pan-European context. In particular, so far, his research activity has focused on issues related to European metropolitan governance in the first instance and Italian metropolitan governance in the second, cohesion policy and its related governance structures at the European, national and metropolitan levels and finally sustainable urbanization and land consumption with particular focus on different laws and spatial planning systems that regulate the territory. Donato has actively participated in recent years in various international research projects such as ESPON SUPER, ESPON SUPER spin-off, ESPON METRO, GREENFORCE and ESPON NOSTAGEO.

Kejt Dhrami, Ph.D., is lecturer at Polis University (FPMMU) since 2015. Currently she is coordinator for planning studies in the MSc program, as well as coordinator for spatial planning and GIS in the professional master program. Kejt's academic experiences include subjects such as: planning history; advanced urban development laboratory; final thesis studio; and, previously, planning systems; GIS; urban planning laboratory; urban policies; etc. Alongside her academic engagement, Kejt is also employed as a spatial planning and regional development expert at Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development, where she currently manages the Territorial Governance Unit. Her skills extend to GIS database systems management and operationalization. Kejt has managed several initiatives / activities

within international projects, funded by USAID, World Bank, IADSA, UNDP, etc., as well as Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects.

Aleksandar Djordjevic works as an associate professor at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography. With a background as spatial planner and GIS analyst, his research revolves around the GIS projects implementation, geospatial analyses, and mapping. Dr Djordjevic coordinated numerous GIS projects on local, regional, and national level in Serbia, as well as within international institutions and companies. His current research interests include the "spatialisation" and visualization of just green transition in the European and Western Balkan's contexts.

Vesna Garvanlieva Andonova is an expert on municipal finance, public finance management, and economic analyses. She has significant professional experience and record in project management and consultancy both for the private and the public sector aimed at economic development. Her interest focuses on quantitative and qualitative research and policy analyses in the areas of good governance in public finance management, human capital development, local finance, regional development, etc.

Alberto Giacometti is a Senior Research Advisor at Nordregio. He has a background in human geography, regional development, and spatial planning. Alberto works in projects related to regional innovation systems, resilience, governance, and circular economy. His research interests surround the governance and territorial aspects of industrial path creation, including the ongoing just green transition.

Isabella Lami graduated with honors in Architecture, Ph.D in "Real Estate and Urban Planning", MSc in "Real Estate and Urban Planning", is Full Professor in Planning Evaluation and Project Appraisal at the Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST), Politecnico di Torino, Italy. She currently teaches "Project appraisal" at the MSc degree in Architecture Construction and City and "Plans and projects appraisal" at the bachelor's degree in "Territorial, urban planning and landscape-environmental planning", both at the Politecnico di Torino. She is an expert in urban and territorial transformation assessment procedures, both qualitative and quantitative, with a particular focus on the multi-dimensionality of the aspects involved and the integration of the different phases of the decision-making – design process. In this regard, she has extensive experience in Multi-Criteria Decision Analyses (MCDA), Problem Structuring Methods (PSMs) and decision-making processes in the context of urban and territorial transformations, as well as in the management of participatory processes. Besides this area, another line of research concerns theoretical reflections and the development of models for the assessment of sustainability in urban areas.

Marjan Nikolov is the President of CEA and a global PPP expert with a PhD in measuring the efficiency of decentralization. He has worked in more than 15 countries in Europe, the Middle East and Africa. His area of expertise covers municipal finance and fiscal decentralization, public financial management, PPP feasibility studies, fiscal transparency and monitoring and cost-benefit analysis. He has prepared, designed and implemented trainings, research papers and policy-making papers on public financial management and decentralization and has professional experience in numerous assignments in the area of public finances, decentralization, macroeconomics. Specific expertise with the focus in: transitional

and development economics, econometrics and statistics, public-private partnership, lecturer/trainer, etc.

Branko Protic is a PhD candidate at the Department for Spatial Planning, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography. The focus of his scientific and professional work is on topics related to spatial and urban planning, infrastructure development and tourism planning. He is an active member of the Serbian Spatial Planners Association (vice-president from 2021) and member of the Serbian Town Planners Association, Serbian Geographical Society, an associate of the Regional Center of Young Talents Belgrade 2.

Carlos Tapia works as Senior Research Fellow at Nordregio, an international research center for regional development and planning located in Stockholm (Sweden). With a background as regional economist and data analyst, his research revolves around the role of green policies for inclusive territorial development. Dr Tapia has conducted and coordinated international research on climate adaptation, green economy, green innovation, and circular economy, including the ESPON GREECO and CIRCTER projects. His current research interests include the social and territorial impacts of climate policies and the implementation of a just green transition in the European and Nordic contexts.

Merita Toska is a Lecturer in Scientific Master Programs at the Faculty of Planning, Environment and Urban Management at POLIS University (Tirana, Albania). Her academic career started at the University of Bologna (Italy), continued in 2007 at the University of Our Lady of Good Counsel (Tirana) and from 2015 at POLIS University as a Lecturer and Researcher. At the same time, Dr Toska is an Expert with over 15 years of professional experience in economic development and public finance issues (engaged in more than 35 national and international projects) at Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development.

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by measuring and mapping resilience, since the adopted methodologies enables us to localise the places where the interventions are required to adapt and/or structurally change the system.

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Annex 5 – Green FORCE Preparatory REPORT – Summer School 2023

Green**FORCE**

Preparatory REPORT
Summer School 2023

Cities in Just Green Transitions

Towards a 2030 climate-neutral strategy for Turin

Dates of the Summer School: 5 July 2023 (online kick-off meeting), 18-22 September 2023 (activities in Turin), October – November 2023 (online intermediate and final presentations).

POLITO – Giancarlo Cotella, Andrea Ajmar, Erblin Berisha, Grazia Brunetta, Ombretta Calderice, Martina Caputo, Donato Casavola, Ketevan Katcharava, Isabella M. Lami, Danial Mohabat Doost, Yahya Shaker, Aida Shaneh, Elena Todella.

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Nordregio – Carlos Tapia, Alberto Giacometti

UB-GEF – Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic

CEA – Marjan Nikolov, Vesna Garvanlieva

Involved universities and institutions: Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development (coordinating partner, AL); Polis University (AL); Politecnico di Torino – R3C Responsible Risk Resilience Centre (IT), Nordregio (SE), University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography (RS) and Center for Economic Analyses Association (MK).

The summer school involves up to 10 selected POLITO students within the framework of the HORIZON-WIDERA project "GreenFORCE. Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans."

The activity **provides 2 ECTS credits** to the participating students. The activity is organised with the support of the POLITO School of Planning and Design.

Project website: <https://greenforcetwinning.net/> Contacts: erblin.berisha@polito.it; elena.todella@polito.it

Local partner

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Summer school introduction

The summer school in Turin is organised jointly by the [Interuniversity Department of Urban and Regional Studies and Planning](#) and the [Interdepartmental Responsible Risk Resilience Centre \(R3C\)](#) of Politecnico di Torino and is set in the framework of the School of Planning and Design and supported by [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) in Albania as the coordinating partner; [University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography \(UB-GEF\)](#) in Serbia and the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden.

It aims to involve students from different universities in identifying the challenges and opportunities of just and green transitions in Turin's post-carbon city context. The main challenge is operationalising the green transition principles in the study's specific context. To face it, spatial and landscape planning instruments and decision-making strategies should be coordinated within a coherent and integrated framework.

The students will attend several lectures and working group activities that introduce the challenges they will have to focus on and present possible ways to approach them. Besides the local perspective, students will learn from European and Western Balkans examples and case studies.

They will be supervised and mentored by an international, multi-disciplinary teaching staff during their activity.

The context: Turin from post-industrial to post-carbon city

Turin is known as the most representative Italian industrial city, which played a significant role in Italy's industrialization over the past century, primarily due to the presence of FIAT car manufacturing, while also being home to various other important industries in sectors like aerospace, railway engineering, electronics, etc.

In a global context, the early to mid-20th century marked a transformative period in industrial practices with the introduction of mass production and assembly-line manufacturing principles pioneered by Henry Ford, the founder of the Ford Motor Company. The transformations in the production processes led to a peak in industrialization in certain countries, what we today call the second industrial revolution. During this period -also known as the Fordist era- a number of cities worldwide implemented the Fordist principles, making them the centers of industrialization and economic growth. In Italy, the city which followed such an influential transition was Turin, considered the archetypical Italian Fordist city.

More particularly, in Turin, FIAT and other major industries began flourishing from the late 1890s onwards. From the 1910s to the 1940s, industrial sites underwent a reorganization, shifting towards more centralized structures based on the Fordist ideas. Symbols of this urban reorganization are the concentration of big production sites in the city.

This transition is best represented in the construction of the Fiat Lingotto plant inaugurated in 1923, an incredibly modern and enormous facility organized according to the assembly line system devised by Ford.

Between the 1920s and 1930s, approximately 12,000 workers and 500 employees worked in this building.

Fiat Lingotto plant – source: [lingotto turin gallery](#)

Urbanization in Turin from 1850s to 1980s – data source: [MuseoTorino](#) – elaborated by the author

In addition, new road infrastructures were created to respond to both the rapid urbanization and the Fordist promotion of car-dependent cities.

This prompted an unprecedented reflection in the city's image, previously well known for its Baroque, Rococo, and neo-classical architecture.

Later in the 1970s, Turin's industrial system employed around 300.000 workers, leading to population growth and rapid urbanization.

The impacts of this trend in Turin were not limited only to the industrial buildings, and the city faced a profound transformation toward constructing large building blocks for public housing neighborhoods, collective services, and leisure spaces.

Torino, Piazza San Carlo 1970 - source: [MuseoTorino](#)

Throughout the 1980s and 1990s, economic recessions, financial crises, globalization in the world economy, and innovative technological advancements led to the decline of Fordist industrial production.

Therefore, Turin faced several challenges, mainly because of the downfall of major industries, including automotive and manufacturing. Some of these challenges were the high unemployment rate, depopulation, decrease in public finance, urban decay, and the need to redefine the city's image and identity.

Spina Centrale and the Porta Susa station - data source:
[openhousetorino](#)

OGR - Officine Grandi Riparazioni – source: [OGRTORINO](#)

Accordingly, the city took the initiative to renovate its image, reshape its development path, and favor the reconversion of its industrial sites, mostly located on the central backbone railway – the so-called "Spina Centrale."

The area is a 12 km long avenue that goes through the city from north to south, created by covering the old railway tracks. According to the 1995 General Master Plan, the requalification of the railway tracks and the simultaneous reconnection of two long-separated parts of the city through a wide urban boulevard has become one of the main drivers of the city's real estate, economic growth, and social

development. Today, the "Spina Centrale" Avenue the railway tracks, known as Spina 1, 2, 3, and 4, passes through four large ex-industrial areas alongside progressing from south to north.

Transforming Turin's industrial areas was associated with significant planning and has required the involvement of a complex urban governance regime. While significant progress has been made, the transition remains ongoing as the city still faces various challenges, such as pollution, industrial specialization, and socio-spatial marginalization.

In response to these challenges and considering the urgent need to deal with global climate change impacts, the European Commission has selected the city of Turin as one of the 100 "[Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030](#)" to become an essential hub of experimentation and innovation about climate matters at a European level.

According to the program, the selected cities are supposed to lead Europe's zero-carbon transition, and contribute to enhancing citizens' well-being through adequate decarbonization efforts. The European Commission's Mission Board supports and guides them in this challenge for climate-neutral and smart cities through a multi-level, co-creative process that will be formalized in a Climate City Contract tailored to each city. The Mission Board is aligned with Europe's Green Deal strategy, to reach to climate-neutrality in Europe by 2050. The achievement of zero carbon in an inclusive manner needs systemic reasoning and strategies to be pursued by cities. Accordingly, at the local level, the City of Turin is already beginning a dialogue with key institutions and strategic partners to jointly pursue actions that can enable the ambitious goal of climate neutrality.

This summer school positions within this articulated process, and it challenges the selected students to explore possible transition and transformation paths. By doing so, they learn from Turin's experiences, which can be then transferred and applied to other contexts in Europe and beyond. In a broader context, the students will be encouraged to reflect on the just and green transitions as complex, multi-faceted phenomena that redefine mainstream development models towards a more socio-environmental and carbon-neutral society.

Just Green Transitions

This introductory section seeks to present the notion of Just Green Transitions without however, having the ambition to be exhaustive. Its objective is to present some entry points to the participants and to get familiar with the key issues.

What are Just Green Transitions (JGT)

Even though there is growing attention on what JGT concept and how to operationalize them, there is no shared or common definition at a conceptual and theoretical levels. Yet, JGT could possibly be perceived as a multifaceted-compound-concept currently developing since "Green Transition" and "Just Transition" have been gaining a foothold of interest among scholars, decision-makers, politicians, and businesses since the European Union (EU) declared its European Green Deal (EGD) (European Commission, [2019](#)). The term Just Green Transitions in its pluralist form is set to emphasize that there are various and simultaneous paths to achieve the so-called sustainable future. These paths may vary according to various geopolitical, political, social, geographic, economic, climatic, and environmental contexts (Shaker and Berisha, 2023).

Just Transition Mechanism (JTM)

The **European Green Deal (EGD)** is the European Commission's roadmap for making the EU's economy sustainable by turning climate and environmental challenges into opportunities across all policy areas and making the transition just and inclusive for all. It outlines investments needed and financing tools available and explains how to ensure a just and inclusive transition. The EGD covers all sectors of the economy, transport, energy, agriculture, buildings, and industries. Despite the predicaments resulting from the ongoing pandemic and the escalation of the global energy crisis, the EU has spared not effort to ensure a geopolitical and socioeconomic recovery of its Member States (MS) and neighbouring countries by introducing a series of initiatives, reforms, and support packages, and funds (European Commission, 2022).

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The European Commission (EC) has launched the **Just Transition Funds (JTF) and the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM)** to make sure that the transition towards a climate-neutral future could be executed inclusively and justly. The JTM is a key tool to ensure that the transition towards a climate-neutral economy happens in a fair way, leaving no one behind. It provides targeted support to help mobilize around €55 billion over the period 2021-2027 in the most affected regions to alleviate the socio-economic impact of the transition. Each Member State must adopt a **Territorial Just Transitions Plan (TJTP)** defining a strategy for supporting territories in the transitional path. The identification of these territories is carried out through a dialogue with the Commission. These TJTPs set out the challenges in each territory and the development needs and objectives to be met by 2030. They identify the types of operations envisaged and specify governance mechanisms.

JGT: Just Transition + Green Transition?

From a diachronic perspective, some notions have been (partially) introduced since the 1950s during the post-WWII reconstruction which have caused enormous environmental impacts and not only. Since then, there has been a growing attention on the issue by incorporating (incrementally) other meanings.

1950s: "[Green Revolution and Great Transformation](#)" (Pfister, [2010](#); Bengtsson et al., 201).

1950s: "[Green Revolution and Great Transformation](#)" (Pfister, [2010](#); Bengtsson et al., 2018).

1970s: "[Just Transition](#)" (The Trades Union Congress, [2012](#); Pinker, 2020).

2015: United Nations [2030 Agenda](#) and the [Paris Agreement](#) (UNFCCC, 2015).

2018: EU [2050 Long-term Strategy Timeline](#)), [Just Transition Mechanism](#) (JTM).

2030: Delivery of EU [2030 Climate Target Plan](#)

2050: Delivery of the European Green Deal.

In the 1970s, Tony Mazzocchi of the US Oil, Chemical and Atomic Workers Union (OCAW) was one of the firsts to have advocated for policies addressing job losses related to environmental regulations; **Just Transition**. In 2015, Just Transition was included in the Paris Agreement (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, [2015](#)) and in 2019 during the United Nations Climate Action Summit, 46 nations committed to just transitions strategies (United Nations, [2019](#); Tavares, [2022](#)).

What's New?

is the combination of both concepts "just transition" and "green transition" into a unique concept; taking into consideration how to conceptualize and implement it.

Just: Social Justice + Spatial Justice

The notion of "Just" might be observed from two different (but not in a dichotomic) perspectives: social justice and spatial justices.

Social justice - having its roots in political philosophy, different disciplines including sociology, social psychology, law and jurisprudence, and human geography, among others have contributed to its theoretical underpinnings and to defining its fundamentals. Humans are social, spatial, and temporal beings (Soja, 2009); they socially produce and construct human relations which forms spaces. From a spatial perspective, the Just dimension goes beyond the concept the spatial configurations, and the processes of producing the space into the process of governing and planning the space and the interactions of the actors with the space in a dynamic and direct democratic process towards social equity in space; a just process that aims at a just product (Shaker and Berisha,2023a,b).

Spatial justice – reaches beyond fair distribution of resources, opportunities, and benefits within a specific geographic area or territory; different communities and regions could experience unequal access to essential services and opportunities; It is the middle ground between physical space, social dynamics, and power structures. It acknowledges that urban and rural areas may have various levels of infrastructure, public services, and economic opportunities, leading to disparities in quality of life and well-being. Spatial justice seeks to challenge these disparities and advocate for policies and interventions that promote more equitable spatial outcomes. Having a strong political dimension, spatial justice is, at the same time, an objective, a process and product of governance and decision-making process (Shaker and Berisha,2023a, b).

Green: Sustainable Eco-Friendly Transition

Green Transition, a concept that started appearing since the 1950s, calling the attention sustainable transformation as a process of change in production, consumption, and personal habits (Pfister, 2010). However, since 1824, without specifically naming it Greenhouse effect, Joseph Fourier and John Tyndall discovered changes and increases in global temperatures. By the launch of the modern environmental debates during 1960s, and as the Green Revolution (Gaud,1968) started to expand globally, several economic, environmental goals, and policy agreements have been in contrast (Söderholm, 2020); various ecological chronicles started to highlight the importance of coordination and preparedness for possible climate disasters and natural hazards which have been frequently happening and is drastically endangering the existence on Earth (IPCC, 2013). Over the past decades, countries, regions, cities, corporates, and individuals have been voluntarily but inconsistently, publicly, and officially announcing their commitment to slogans such as sustainable development, eco-friendly, natural-based, net-zero and green transition (Shaker and Berisha,2023a, b).

Transitions

Transition is a concept that indicates "a process or a period of changing from one state or condition to another" or "a change or shift from one state, subject, place, etc. to another." In the field of policy, transition can indicate both the process as well as the aim – transitioning from a specific state to another that can addressed by a policy or a set of policies. Consequently, transitions, are institutional; multi-level, cross-sectorial (socio-political, socio-spatial, socio-technical, socio-ecological) influenced by ideologies, traditions, values, ideas, ethics, morals, and perceptions

(Cedergren et al., 2022; Hansen and Coenen, 2015; Kemp et al., 2007; Rotmans and Kemp 2003) and imply radical changes (Loorbach et al., 2019) and are rooted in uncertainty of changes (Handmer & Dovers, 1996); shifting from a status-quo to a visionary one. Transitions from a carbon-based economy to a sustainable zero-net carbon society has implicit (and often explicit) costs (European Commission, 2023a) and could result in creating and/or increasing burdens over individuals, societies, regions, nations, and continents. However, what exactly sustainability means, and what it entails in space-time is changing and it is itself constant transition. The transitional period is set to allow individuals and societies to move from a carbon-based economy to a zero-net carbon one. This transition is ought to be society sensible, meaning "**no one nor region should be left behind**" as forecasted. To ensure that transitions are undertaken sustainably they ought to meet the needs of present generations not compromising future generations' possibilities to meet their contemporary needs (United Nations, 1987).

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Main thematic Issues

The Turin context will be analysed on the 4 major issues that are characterizing the international debate on the just green transitions of the cities of the future: (i) Urban regeneration (**spatial/social justice**); (ii) Energy and digital transition (**multiple and simultaneous transitions**); (iii) Climate change, resilience, green infrastructures (**green transition**); (iv) Indicators and their spatialisation.

Thematic Issue 1 - Urban regeneration (spatial/social justice)

According to what was presented in describing the context, urban regeneration has been involved and will continue to involve a variety of actors and stakeholders as local authorities, citizens, businesses, investors regional and national authorities. In the case of Turin, they will be focus to on:

- Deliver 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030
- Ensure that these cities act as experimentation and innovation hubs to enable all European cities to follow suit by 2050
- As foreseen in its implementation plan, the transition will be multiple and will affect several aspects/sectors

In this respect, great attention will be devoted to the question of spatial and social justice ensuring that no one will be left behind. This is particularly important regarding the:

- Green areas accessibility
- Housing affordability (avoiding gentrification)
- Access to services

Thematic Issue 2 - Energy and digital transition (multiple and simultaneous transitions)

As above mentioned, transitions are multiple and simultaneous. In this respect, this thematic issue will focus on:

- Energy transition by exploring the potentialities of the city of Turin regarding this issue.
- Digital transition towards a "smarter" society, reducing digital divide and increasing digital accessibility.
- Technological transition towards a more efficient and effective industrial sector etc.

Thematic Issue 3 - Climate change, resilience, green infrastructures (green transition)

The "green" dimension of JGT will be explored by the issues of:

- Climate change, how climate change can affect the future development of the city.
- Resilience, what is needed for making a city more resilient internal and external stimuli.
- Green infrastructure(s) as implementable projects and local scale to reduce climate change and increase territorial resilience.

Thematic Issue 4 - Indicators and their spatialisation

This thematic issue is a horizontal one, meaning that, each JTC thematic issue presented will focus also in identifying representative indicators. Those indicators, when possible, will be spatialised by GIS tools/instruments.

List of useful documents and links

Entity	Websites of reference
Piedmont Region	https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/
Città metropolitana di Torino	http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/
Comune di Torino	http://www.comune.torino.it/
Geoportale Regione Piemonte	https://www.geoportale.piemonte.it/cms/
Geoportale Comune di Torino	http://geoportale.comune.torino.it/web/
Torino 2030	https://www.torinovivibile.it/torino-2030/
Torino social impact	https://www.torinosocialimpact.it/ecosistema/torino-urban-lab/
Urban lab Torino	https://urbanlabtorino.it/
Piano strategico di Torino 2000	Il Piano strategico della città. 2000 Byterfly
Piano strategico di Torino 2021-2023	La visione del PSM 2021-2023 - Città Metropolitana di Torino... (cittametropolitana.torino.it)
Piano regolatore del comune di Torino	http://geoportale.comune.torino.it/web/governo-del-territorio/piano-regolatore-generale
Piano Urbano di Torino della mobilità sostenibile	http://geoportale.comune.torino.it/web/sezioni-tematiche/piano-urbano-della-mobilita-sostenibile-introduzione
Catalogo data Torino	http://geoportale.comune.torino.it/geocatalogocoto/?sezione=catalogo
Parco Piemontese	http://www.parcopiemontese.it/
100 Net Zero Cities	https://netzerocities.eu/
Eurocities	https://eurocities.eu/latest/the-100-climate-neutral-and-smart-cities-by-2030/
Carbon neutrality and smart cities EU	Climate-neutral and smart cities (europa.eu)
Mappe Geoportale	http://geoportale.comune.torino.it/geocatalogocoto/?sezione=mappa
R3C lab Torino	http://www.r3c.polito.it/
Copernicus	https://www.copernicus.eu/it
SDG11lab Torino	https://sdg11.polito.it/it
Geomatics lab Torino	https://areeweb.polito.it/geomatics_lab/it/

The agenda – main presentations

Presentation 1 - Territorial Resilience and Just Green Transitions

Grazia Brunetta and Ombretta Caldarice, DIST, Politecnico di Torino, Responsible Risk Resilience interdepartmental Centre R3C

Abstract

The 2018 CitiesIPCC Research and Action Agenda outlined that currently cities face critical global challenges, related to environmental changes, social crises, critical infrastructure failures, terrorist attacks, technological accidents, and the recent pandemic. To provide a broad answer to climate change and socio-economic uncertainties, cities worldwide have already started to develop specific mitigation and/or adaptation policies/plans/actions in the perspective of territorial resilience. Territorial resilience aims to increase the ability of territorial systems to respond systemically and dynamically to present and future shocks and stresses related to major global challenges: unsustainable development patterns, rapid and unplanned urbanisation, climate change effects. In this scenario, the Green Transition aims to overcome the challenges coming from climate change impacts and environmental threads in European Union. Green Transition could be framed appropriately within the resilience-oriented policies and plans since the main objective of Green Transition regards climate neutrality by 2050. At the same time, resilience-based policies and solutions through adaptation and mitigation strategies tries to reduce the adverse effects of climate change on societies. Starting from this framework, the lecture will frame the concept of territorial resilience, from its roots in ecology to resilience thinking in spatial planning welcoming the just green transition in the planning process. Students will develop their theoretical knowledge on the fundamentals of territorial resilience in global challenges science and in the international policies.

Bios

Grazia Brunetta is Professor of Urban Planning at DIST Politecnico di Torino. She is Scientific coordinator of the Responsible Risk Resilience interdepartmental Centre (R3C) of Politecnico di Torino, where she is the scientific coordinator of an interdisciplinary research team that aims to enhance cities forward resilience in planning and policy. Her main research activities show a deep and constant involvement in the field of urban and regional planning, with a particular focus on the innovation in the theories, methodologies, and approaches for spatial planning, in both research and academic teaching activity. She is the scientific coordinator of 2nd level specialising master programme in *Metodi e Tecniche per il governo di territori resilienti. Verso la gestione integrata dei rischi*. She is member of the Expert committee of the Intensive Training on Urban Resilience organized by University of Southern Denmark, Aalborg University, and BloxHub Copenhagen. She is the scientific coordinator of a wide range of research on regional and environmental planning, dealing with institutional innovation in spatial planning, evaluation in planning, spatial analysis for regional development, urban resilience in planning and design. On these topics she has been coordinator of many international and national research teams and invited speaker in national and international conferences. She has authored more than 250 publications.

Ombretta Caldarice is Assistant Professor in Urban and Regional Planning at the Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST), Politecnico di Torino. She is a Faculty Affiliate Member of the Responsible Risk Resilience Centre - R3C, Politecnico di Torino. Her research activities focus on the interplay between planning and urban resilience through the lens of planning rules. She has more than ten years of international experience in research, capacity-building, and education on how to make cities more resilient, dealing with the following topics: (i) theories and practices of resilience; (ii) mainstreaming resilience in spatial planning; and (iii) urban codes and techniques for resilience. She is the co-coordinator of the ERASMUS+ Project with the

Witwatersrand University Johannesburg on resilience and climate change. She is a member of the scientific committee of the Intensive Training on Urban Resilience (University of Southern of Denmark). She is a member of the Editorial Board of the Springer Book Series "Resilient Cities. Rethinking Urban Transformation."

Presentation 2 - Spatio-temporal variability of Just Green Transitions indicators

Andrea Ajmar, Erblin Berisha, Elena Todella (POLITO), Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic (UB-GEF)

Abstract

Geomatics' techniques, remote sensing, and GIS, play a consolidated and scientifically recognised role in urban and regional planning and for implementing just green transitions (JGT) policies and interventions.

Indicators represent an effective solution to monitor the status of the environment and to measure progress in respect to specific targets.

Within this module, you will learn a set of indicators representative of JGT, how to analyse and spatially them by means of:

- Exploitation of (geospatial) data catalogues for retrieving relevant data to feed the indicators;
- Organisation and pre-processing of the relevant input data, with hints on methods for filling data gaps;
- Usage of GIS methods and tools to generate value-added information by combining spatial and non-spatial datasets;
- Data representation and communication.

The practical exercise consists in evaluating urban green areas accessibility within Torino municipality by:

- Accessing to relevant high-resolution land-use/landcover dataset (i.e., Urban Atlas) and generating visualisations and statistics about the presence of green areas;
- Exploiting road network datasets to perform physical accessibility analysis to green areas;
- Combining physical accessibility with socio-demographic (census) datasets to estimate social equality/inclusion.

The methodology learned during the session will allow you to apply the same indicator over different geographical areas and to develop/calculate new indicators.

Bios

Andrea Ajmar is an associate professor at Politecnico di Torino: he holds a doctorate in Environmental Geoengineering and is an expert in analysis in GIS environment and in the development and implementation of Spatial Data Infrastructures. He is a member of the SDG11Lab laboratory which aims to create a spatial data infrastructure capable of guaranteeing efficient access to data sources of general interest (e.g., satellite and airborne acquisitions, reference cartographic data, etc.) and integrate them with specific thematic data, providing analysis, representation, and visualization tools for research activities. He is involved in several research projects and in operational cartographic production services, both at the national and European level.

Erblin Berisha is an assistant professor at the Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST) of Politecnico di Torino. His research focuses on the evolution of Spatial Planning Systems and Territorial Governance in the Western Balkan region in the light of international influence. He is also interested in understanding the impact of Green Just Transitions in the Western Balkans. Moreover, he has been teaching Adriatic Ionian Cooperation module at the Politecnica delle Marche, Faculty of Economy, Ancona, Italy.

Aleksandar Djordjevic works as an associate professor at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography. With a background as spatial planner and GIS analyst, his research revolves around the GIS projects implementation, geospatial analyses, and mapping. Dr Djordjevic coordinated numerous GIS projects on local, regional, and national level in Serbia, as well as within international institutions and companies. His current research interests include the "spatialisation" and visualization of just green transition in the European and Western Balkans contexts.

Branko Protic is a PhD candidate at the Department for Spatial Planning, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography. The focus of his scientific and professional work is on topics related to spatial and urban planning, infrastructure development and tourism planning. He is an active member of the Serbian Spatial Planners Association (vice-president from 2021) and member of the Serbian Town Planners Association, Serbian Geographical Society, an associate of the Regional Center of Young Talents Belgrade 2.

Elena Todella is a post-Doc research fellow at Politecnico di Torino, Italy. She currently teaches "Real Estate Appraisal" at the bachelor's degree in "Building Engineering and Architecture" at the Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna and she is assistant professor in "Theories and tools for real estate valuations" at the bachelor's degree course in "Architecture" at the Politecnico di Torino. Her research strands concern Problem Structuring Methods (PSMs) and the structuring of complex urban transformations. Her research activity related to visualization models and tools to support decision-making, straddling the line between evaluation and architectural design.

Presentation 3 - Environmental and Social Cost Benefit Analysis (SE-CBA)

Merita Toska (Co-Plan/U_Polis)

Abstract

The lecture aims to introduce the audience to the Social Environmental Cost Benefit Analysis (SE-CBA) as an instrument to assess, among others, the impact of green transition actions. SE-CBA extends the conventional cost-benefit analysis to encompass a broader range of costs and benefits, considering the social and environmental effects that society may experience due to the intervention. The day will be organised in two parts: a content section setting the background for SE-SBA (SBA, Feasibility Studies according to EU guidelines) and a practical session carried out in groups (using a case study from Prishtina Urban Regeneration Program).

The first part of the day will cover the topic of SE-CBA from a methodological point of view: what is a SE-CBA, its use, advantages and disadvantages of the instrument, the distinction between the conventional CBA, the financial and economic feasibility studies, and business plans. The methodological approach for the SE-CBA will include: (i) setting -up the framework for SE-CBA, (ii) identification of the costs and benefits to be recognised and caused by an intervention; (iii) quantification of the costs and benefits; (iv) monetisation of costs and benefits; (v) discounting rate and discounting of costs and benefits; (vi) computation of indicators (net present value), internal rate of return and benefits to costs ratio), and (vii) sensitivity analysis.

In the second part of the day, students will be introduced to an applied exercise. A case study from Prishtina Urban Regeneration Program (a World Bank Project) will be presented, and a practical exercise will be conducted in Excel (templates and case studies will be provided in advance).

Bio

Dr Merita Toska is a Lecturer in Scientific Master Programs at the Faculty of Planning, Environment and Urban Management at POLIS University (Tirana, Albania). Her academic career started at the University of Bologna (Italy), continued in 2007 at the University of Our Lady of Good Counsel (Tirana) and from 2015 at POLIS University as a Lecturer and Researcher. At the same time, Dr Toska is an Expert with over 15 years of professional experience in economic development and public finance issues (engaged in more than 35 national and international projects) at Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development.

Presentation 4 - A case study in North Macedonia: cost-benefit analysis for coal thermal plant decommissioning – work in progress

Vesna Garvanlieva and Marjan Nikolov (CEA)

Abstract

The presentation will demonstrate the status of a work-in-progress preparation of a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) of a case for thermal plant decommissioning during an implementation of research in progress. The presentation will provide a short theoretical part followed by an example of practical perspective of what an input-output analysis is and how it may be used in development of an CBA scenarios through the case of planned decarbonization through closure of a plant in a specific region. The goal of the I/O segment of the presentation will be to introduce I/O as one of many methods for monetizing socio-economic effects arising from the complexity and interlinkages between different economic sectors. Furthermore, the presentation will give an overview of the CBA as a method to link the I/O in one of the stages in carrying out CBA scenario comparison. Firstly, though the case of the TPP in SWPR in North Macedonia the potential gainers or losers will be identified, the timing, after which the impacts will be assigned monetary values for selection of costs/benefits such as on the regional gross added value, the labor and employment as social aspects, environmental health costs etc. CBA is not a stringent assessment method thus through example of few methods for monetization of the impact will be presented for the students to gain a perspective for their potential future research to take an interest in the and to potentially put into practice in the future.

Bios

Vesna Garvanlieva Andonova is an expert on municipal finance, public finance management, and economic analyses. She has significant professional experience and record in project management and consultancy both for the private and the public sector aimed at economic development. Her interest focuses on quantitative and qualitative research and policy analyses in the areas of good governance in public finance management, human capital development, local finance, regional development, etc.

Marjan Nikolov is the President of CEA and a global PPP expert. His area of expertise covers municipal finance and fiscal decentralization, public financial management, PPP feasibility studies, fiscal transparency and monitoring and cost-benefit analysis. He has prepared, designed, and implemented trainings, research papers and policy-making papers on public financial management and decentralization and has professional experience in numerous assignments in the area of public finances, decentralization, macroeconomics. Specific expertise with the focus in transitional and development economics, econometrics and statistics, public-private partnership, lecturer/trainer, etc.

Presentation 5 - Land-Based Financing for Climate Solutions

Kejt Dhrami (Co-Plan/U_Polis)

Abstract

The session will introduce an emerging approach that seeks to harness the potential of land markets to fund and promote sustainable land use practices and nature-based solutions. The session aims to equip students with a background understanding of land markets, value capture instruments, and surplus value calculations (residual land value for public use) in the context of resilient urban development. The first part of the session is a theoretical one and will introduce the concept of land markets, exploring the dynamics of supply and demand and the factors that influence land values. Following, we will delve into value capture instruments, an essential tool in financing nature-based and climate solutions (but not only). Through case studies from Latin America, USA, Asia and pilot research cases in Albania, students will learn about a few key mechanisms of land value capture, such as impact fees; betterment fees; property taxation; transfer of development rights; bonus FAR; land readjustment; inclusionary housing; etc. These instruments enable governments and stakeholders to capture a portion of the increased land value resulting from infrastructure investments and development projects, to re-invest in climate solutions in the city and/or the area. The second part of the session will encompass a gaming exercise, where a land purchase process will be simulated in 2 scenarios: 1st scenario is an unregulated land market with uninformed stakeholders; and the 2nd scenario is a regulated land market; with informed stakeholders. The students will be provided with materials beforehand to facilitate the gaming process. The third part of the session will be embedded into the studio work during the afternoon, where students will be assigned a specific value-capture instrument to pilot for their respective group work and will calculate preliminary costs and benefits for the engaged stakeholders: landowners; developers and public government. Through this teaching session and exercise, students will be empowered to explore innovative ways to finance and implement climate solutions, contributing to a more resilient future.

Bio

Kejt DHRAMI (PhD) is lecturer at Polis University (FPMU) since 2015. Currently she is coordinator for planning studies in the MSc program, as well as coordinator for spatial planning and GIS in the professional master program. Kejt's academic experiences include subjects such as: planning history; advanced urban development laboratory; final thesis studio; and, previously, planning systems; GIS; urban planning laboratory; urban policies; etc. Alongside her academic engagement, Kejt is also employed as a spatial planning and regional development expert at CO-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development, where she currently manages the Territorial Governance Unit. Her skills extend to GIS database systems management and operationalization. Kejt has managed several initiatives / activities within international projects, funded by USAID, World Bank, IADSA, UNDP, etc., as well as Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects.

Presentation 6 - Just Green Transition: between carbon-neutrality and re-industrialisation

Carlos Tapia and Alberto Giacometti (Nordregio)

Abstract

The aim of Day 4 is to challenge the dominant narrative of the JGT which focuses on the negative impacts (on labour) of decommissioning 'obsolete' industries and energy systems and brings to light the challenges of adaptation to new technological regimes and re-industrialisation. The focus is placed on the planning challenges

linked to processes of rapid and massive re-industrialization. The day, led by Carlos Tapia and Alberto Giacometti from Nordregio, will be organised into two parts: a content session and a practical exercise carried out in groups.

The content session begins with (1) unwrapping the Just Green Transition (JGT) concept, how it has evolved and interpreted over time, and how the JGT is framed in policy today. Then it (2) delves into the myths and misconceptions surrounding climate change and JGT policies, and how the climate agenda is being 'weaponized' to generate political polarisation and fabricate a 'culture war'. Furthermore, it (3) addresses the sectoral bias in EU's JGT policy in terms of affected sectors and the absent focus on industrial adaptation and re-industrialisation. Finally, it (4) draws on the lessons from Scandinavia and the ongoing processes of 'green industrialisation'.

The practical exercise consists of developing ideas contributing to either 1) a spatial/strategic plan for the Northern Swedish city of Skellefteå, which is currently experiencing a deep transformation generated by the sudden arrival of a major battery gigafactory: Northvolt; and/or 2) sectoral/regional plan for the broader Northernmost regions of Sweden, which are also receiving major investments for industrial reconversion. The teaching staff will introduce the case study areas and detailed material related to planning challenges, socio-economic trends, and governance context. Students will then be split into smaller groups to work on planning and strategic solutions.

Bios

Carlos Tapia works as Senior Research Fellow at Nordregio, an international research center for regional development and planning located in Stockholm (Sweden). With a background as regional economist and data analyst, his research revolves around the role of green policies for inclusive territorial development. Dr Tapia has conducted and coordinated international research on climate adaptation, green economy, green innovation, and circular economy, including the ESPON GREECO and CIRCTER projects. His current research interests include the social and territorial impacts of climate policies and the implementation of a just green transition in the European and Nordic contexts.

Alberto Giacometti is a Senior Research Advisor at Nordregio. He has a background in human geography, regional development, and spatial planning. Alberto works in projects related to regional innovation systems, resilience, governance, and circular economy. His research interests surround the governance and territorial aspects of industrial path creation, including the ongoing just green transition.

The study-visit

The study visit has been organized by POLITICO Team with the assistance and the coordination of Urban Lab. Urban Lab is an independent association set up to describe the transformation of Torino and its metropolitan area. Its purpose is to collect documents, spread knowledge and promote debate about the city. A place where citizens, experts and economic operators can find information, meet, and talk. Urban Lab addresses the citizens interested in urban transformations, leading them in the discovery of Torino's area, its architecture, spaces, and their uses. Also, it offers experts and insiders the possibility to study policies, urban plans, and transformation projects in depth, with a specific focus on local experience and international good practices.

This is a brief introduction to the study visit we have organized. More specifically, Urban Lab, after a presentation, at its headquarters, of the transformations that took place in the city during the period of major industrial disuse and the conversion of these areas into new spaces with uses other than manufacturing, will accompany us around the city to touch and be told about these urban and social transformations. The tour will touch relevant spaces in Turin like Dora Park, Bee Ozanam, Baldissera Square and many others. In the following sections, there is a brief tour presentation.

Dora Park

The park covers an area of 45 hectares where the five industrial areas Ingest, Vitali, Mortara, Valdocco and Michelin once stood. Elaborated following an international competition based on Jean-Pierre Buffi and Andreas Kipar's masterplan, the project by Germany's Latz + Partner with Turin-based Studio Pession recycles materials, structures and routes from the old iron and steel works, metallurgical factories, and tyre factories.

The project is structured according to three key themes: the resurfacing of the Dora River route, the intervention on the remains of the buildings (partially recovered), and the integration of the new park with the city. Green lawns have thus sprung up in the area, integrating the former Michelin cooling tower, transformed into a light and sound sculpture. In the former canteen, the 'A come Ambiente (E for Environment)' Museum. In the Valdocco lot, tree plantings studied recall the grid of the load-bearing structures of the former warehouses. Overhead walkways connect the north side of Valdocco with the Environment Park.

A wide promenade with pergolas and vaults created by tree canopies leads to the residential area instead. The new road tunnel's wall encloses the park's inner space. A wide tree-lined ramp connects the two levels of the park, flanked by the imposing cooling towers. However, the renovation of the former Vitali stripping shed is the project's distinctive and most scenic feature. Here, architecture prevails over greenery. The striking canopy, a cathedral supported by tall, red-painted pillars and emptied of its façade, accommodates a multifunctional space. A footbridge, crossing the busy Via Borgaro, leads to the last lot, that of the former Ingest. Here, next to the Church of the Santo Volto, water tanks and stone gardens alternate in the form of *hortus conclusus*, in what were the concrete bases of the former industrial structures.

The former industrial areas around the Dora Park – source: elaborated by the author

The Dora Park – source: [Le Case nel Parco](#)

Beeozanam

Introduction by Emanuela Saporito, community planner at Beeozanam

Located in a former industrial complex with an original "ship-machine" architecture, Beeozanam is a regenerated space in the name of sustainability with vegetable gardens and roof gardens, a social restaurant, an apiary, and an open and inclusive community hub where ideas, projects and activities can be generated. The community hub is a hybrid space, between production and services, open to citizen participation in its use and management, designed to build on the networks of neighbouring neighborhoods and to grow by exploiting city, national and international networks. The challenge is to combat cultural poverty and social disintegration in the area, stimulating the growth of a 'sustainable generation' through the co-production of cultural, educational, and aggregative activities.

Beeozanam – source: [Labsus](#)

Starting from Beeozanam and ending in Viale Mai, a series of problematic blocks are crossed, as emblematic of this area of Torino.

Baldissera Square

One of the most talked about road junctions in the city due to frequent traffic jams and the cause of strong complaints from citizens.

Baldissera Square – source: [Corriere.it](https://www.corriere.it)

Via Saint Bon and the new line 12

Introduction by Amerigo Strozzi, project manager

The project to redevelop the long railway trench on Via Saint Bon, where the Turin-Ceres line originally ran, will include the new route of Line 12, which will recover the now disused tunnel between the Madonna di Campagna neighborhood and the Dora.

The project of the new line 12 – source: [Mobilità Torino](https://www.mobilita-torino.it)

Former OGM

The FIAT Grandi Motori complex is an important disused industrial area in an almost total state of abandonment due to the gradual exhaustion of production since the 1980s.

Former OGM project – source: [TorinoToday](https://www.torinotoday.it)

Campus Einaudi and Viale Mai

Funded by the
European Union

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Starting from Beeozanam and ending in Viale Mai, a series of problematic blocks are crossed, as emblematic of this area of Torino. Along the Dora River, where "metal" gasometers stand as evidence of the city's industrial past (former Italgas area), sits the new Einaudi Campus, home to the Law and Political Science faculties of the University of Turin. The project signed by Foster & Partners, Camerana & Partners, Tecnimont, Mellano Associati and Giugiaro Architettura, winners of an international competition, creates an organic system of seven pavilions with ribbon facades, arranged around a large circular plaza. Following the triangular shape of the lot, the new addition is functionally divided into two sections: one for teaching and one for the library along the Dora.

The campus – source: [ICIS srl](#)

Between Campus Einaudi and the adjacent student housing is Ottavio Mario Mai street, the subject of a recent redevelopment by the City of Torino. With about 4,500 square meters of pedestrian area equipped for the benefit of students and citizens, this project is part of the interventions financed through the European project Urban Innovative Actions, aimed at improving the livability of public spaces in the areas adjacent to the Dora River, including in the evening and night hours.

Ottavio Mario Mai street – source: [ToNite](#)

Off Topic

Speaker Alessandro Raspaldo, production manager of Off Topic

Off Topic is a center for youth protagonism born thanks to a bet made by the Torino Youth Centre, an association that in 2017 decided to invest in the renovation of spaces for the creation of a new hub for the city. Inside there is a bistro, an enclosed space for theater, music and parties, a multipurpose hall and the courtyard also used for events.

The spaces of the Off Topic – source: [Off Topic](#)

Horizon Europe Programme
HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02-01
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GreenFORCE Project

This students' summer school is part of the HORIZON-WIDERA project "[GreenFORCE. Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans](#)" (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02-02). The five partner organisations are [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) in Albania as the coordinating partner; [University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography \(UB-GEF\)](#) in Serbia and the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden, together with [Politecnico di Torino \(PoliTO\)](#), in Italy, as the leading EU research institutions. POLIS University (U_Polis) in Albania is the affiliate partner of Co-PLAN. GreenFORCE aims to foster excellence in the Western Balkans' green transition scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia); to enhance their research profile, strengthening the research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans and European Union research capacities, as well as to broader policy initiatives for the region. This objective is reached through the twinning partnership of five organisations that work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; transfer and exchange knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle; and engage in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level. The researchers of the consortium engage in building a joint research project with objectives related to (i) the conceptualisation of green transition in the WB; (ii) the assessment of impacts and costs of just green transition, focusing on components of the pillars of the EU green agenda for the WB; (iii) the proposal of a continuous monitoring and assessment framework on green transition impacts and costs in the WB, to be used by scientists, researchers and policy-makers in facilitating the just green transition. This summer school is the first of three stand-alone teaching events that contribute to the co-design, co-evaluation, exchange and sharing of the research practice and results conducted in the project. The events are open to students from U_Polis, UB-GEF and POLITO. Each event will host up to 20 students, of which ten will be from the hosting institution, in this case, POLITO. Students attending at least one of the stand-alone teaching events may decide to work more thoroughly on this topic through the development of their master thesis under the supervision of one or more professors involved in the summer school.

For any clarification, please send an email to both erblin.berisha@polito.it and elena.todella@polito.it.

The activity is organized with the support of the POLITO School of Planning and Design.

General timeline

Date	Before the summer school
15th of May 2023	Launch of the Call for Participation
26th of May 2023	Deadline for students' application
1st of June 2023	Notification of the results
7th of June 2023	Deadline for acceptance and finalization of the list of participants
	Summer school and after
July 2023 (to be defined)	1-day meeting event (online)
18th-22nd of September 2023	summer school activities in Torino
October 2023 (to be defined)	2-days feedback event (online)

Local Organizing Committee

POLITO – Giancarlo Cotella, Andrea Ajmar, Erblin Berisha, Grazia Brunetta, Ombretta Calderice, Martina Caputo, Donato Casavola, Ketevan Katcharava, Isabella M. Lami, Danial Mohabat Doost, Yahya Shaker, Aida Shaneh, Elena Todella.

Spatial Planning
 and Territorial
 Governance

Multicriteria Analysis

Planning for resilience
 and climate change

Spatial Data Science

Prof. Grazia
 Brunetta

Dr. Ombretta
 Calderice

Dr. Erblin Berisha

Dr. Elena
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Prof. Andrea
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 Cotella

Dr. Danial
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